

TRANSLATION OF NEOLOGISMS-PHRASES OF THE MODERN KOREAN LANGUAGE INTO ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the features of the formation of neologisms-phrases in the modern Korean language of the 21st century and features of their translation into English. The analysis showed that most of the neologisms are translated into English using tracing, to the least extent such means of translation as descriptive translation, transcription/transliteration, lexico-semantic transformation is used.

Key words and phrases: neologism; word formation; phrase; free phrases; phraseological unit; translation methods.

ПЕРЕВОД НЕОЛОГИЗМОВ-СЛОВСОЧЕТАНИЙ СОВРЕМЕННОГО КОРЕЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА НА АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются особенности образования неологизмов-словосочетаний в современном корейском языке XXI века и особенности их перевода на английский язык. Анализ показал, что большая часть неологизмов переводится на английский язык с помощью калькирования, в наименьшей степени используются такие средства перевода, как описательный перевод, транскрипция/транслитерация, лексико-семантическая трансформация.

Ключевые слова: неологизм; словообразование; словосочетание; свободные словосочетания; фразеологизм; способы перевода.

ZAMONAVIY KOREYS TILIDAGI NEOLOGIZM-IBORALARNING INGLIZ TILIGA TARJIMASI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada XXI-asrning zamonaviy koreys tilida neologizm-iboralarning shakllanish xususiyatlari va ularni ingliz tiliga tarjima qilish xususiyatlari muhokama qilinadi. Tahlil shuni ko'rsatdiki, neologizmlarning aksariyati ingliz tiliga tracing

yordamida tarjima qilinadi, eng kam darajada tavsifiy tarjima, transkripsiya/transliteratsiya, leksik-semantik transformatsiya kabi tarjima vositalari qo'llaniladi.

Kalit so'zlar: neologizm; so'z yasash; ibora; erkin iboralar; frazeologik birlik; tarjima usullari.

INTRODUCTION

New words appear in the language constantly, at all stages of its existence. During periods of social stability, this process proceeds measuredly and gradually. During the period of social upheaval, the rapid pace of development of society, the processes of language development are accelerated, and the question of their systematization is of particular importance.

THE PURPOSE OF OUR STUDY is to study the features of the functioning of new English word combinations. To achieve this goal, we set the following tasks: to analyze the structural and semantic characteristics of these phrases and ways to translate them into English.

Articles of modern Korean online newspapers, blog texts ("Korean everyday", "Saranghanin Hangugo") in social networks ("Facebook", "Instagram", "Twitter", "Twitch"), data from online and interactive dictionaries ("Naver", "NamuWiki" "National Institute of Korean Language's Korean-English Learners' Dictionary").

THE SCIENTIFIC NOVELTY OF THE STUDY

lies in the fact that the paper proposes a classification of neologisms-phrases (for the period from 2013 to 2021) by areas of use, a comparative analysis of these neologisms in two languages of different structure is carried out: Korean and English; the features of their translation are analyzed.

THE RELEVANCE OF THE WORK is due to the fact that every year the trend towards the use of neologisms-phrases in the language of newspaper and journalistic texts and social networks is increasing. But a review of the literature on the research topic showed that the problem of comparative analysis of neologisms in the two languages under consideration, as well as the translational aspect of this issue, remain not fully understood.

THE PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE WORK lies in the possibility of using the studied material in compiling dictionaries of the new vocabulary of the modern Korean language, in lecture courses on linguistics, lexicology, stylistics, translation theory, in the practice of teaching the Korean language in universities, in translating newspaper texts, in compiling teaching aids for translators.

THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY is based on the classical approach, which includes a theoretical analysis of specialized literature on the research topic, the

choice of texts to be analyzed, statistical processing of the data obtained, and linguistic interpretation of the results obtained. The main methods were: the method of linguistic observation and description (interpretation, generalization and typology of the analyzed material), the method of word-formation analysis, the method of semantic analysis, the comparative method, the method of mathematical analysis, the modeling method.

RELATED WORK

The interest in lexical changes in the Korean language is evidenced by the publication and compilation of new dictionaries. The term "neologism" was borrowed from French in the 19th century. (neologisme - from the Greek neos logos - a new word). O. S. Akhmanova gives the following definition of this term: "A word or phrase created (arising) to designate a new (previously unknown) subject or to express a new concept" [1]. In our work, we adhere to the following definition of the term "phrase" - "it is a combination of two or more significant words, related in meaning and grammatically, serving for a divided designation of a single concept (object, quality, action, etc.)" [3].

At the first stage of the study, the selected phrases were subjected to structural and semantic analysis. In accordance with the classification of phrases by D. E. Rozental and M. A. Telenkova [2], based on the morphological properties of the main word, among the phrases there are:

1. Verbal phrases - with a verb as the main word.
2. Nominal, which are divided into:
 - a) substantive (noun / nominal phrases) - with a noun as the main word;
 - b) adjectival (adjectival phrases) - with an adjective as the main word;
 - c) pronouns (pronominal phrases) - with a pronoun as the main word;
 - d) quantitative (numerical phrases) - with a numeral in the role of the main word.
3. Adverbial phrases - with an adverb as the main word [Ibid., p. 277].

PROPOSED IDEA

1) 핑프 is short for 핑거 프린세스 (Finger princess). An extremely lazy person (cannot lift a finger). Derived from an English expression, widely used in the domestic sphere, when describing a person's character [4].

그 사람이 핑프네~ He's afraid to lift a finger.

Method of translation: tracing

2) 셀카를 찍다 - take a selfie. It came from the English "selfie", that is, to take pictures of oneself.

친구와 함께 셀카를 찍고 싶다 - I want to take a selfie with a friend[5].

Translation method: transcription (transliteration).

3) 애플이 (the first syllable of "Apple"). Fan of Apple products. Due to the widespread use of Apple products, fans of these products are called product fans, or 애플이. Scope of use: household.

새로운 아이폰 나오면 사야겠다 - As soon as the new iPhone comes out, I should immediately buy it

역시 애플이네 - Definitely an Apple fan [6].

Translation method: tracing

4) 있어빌리티 - "ability" (a combination of Korean "isso" (there is, there is) and ability (skill, opportunity)). A term that refers to the use of social networks. A certain trend of behavior, which includes ostentatious "glamor", wealth, wealth and beauty of life. "Pretend you have something, even if it's just for show." [7,8,9,10]

마케팅 있어빌리티 - marketing opportunity (dexterity)

Translation method: descriptive.

5) 버카 - this neologism is a kind of abbreviation of the words 버스 "bus" and 카드 card", i.e. card for paying for bus fares. When translating the neologism in the literal way of translating "bus card", the word takes on two meanings: bus route map, or a card to pay for the fare [11].

넣었는지 기억이 안 나요. - I don't remember where I put my card to pay for the bus fare.

Translation method: descriptive.

6) 비번 is the password. An abbreviation for the Korean words 비밀 meaning secret and 번호 meaning number [12].

나한테 네 비번을 알려 줄 수 있나? - Can you tell me your password?

Translation method: selection of equivalent.

7) 킷킷빠빠 is an abbreviation for the full phrase "킷 때 끼고 빠질 때 빠져" meaning "Join when you need to, pass by when you need to" in the meaning of "know the right time for your actions."

네가 우리와 같이 매일 놀 필요가 없어서 킷킷빠빠. - You don't have to walk with us every day, so join us when you have time.

Translation method: descriptive.

8) 엄크 - initial syllables 엄 from the word 엄마 (mother) and 크 from the word "Critical".

General meaning: the moment in a computer game when the hero dies due to the mother suddenly entering the room [13].

엄크때문에 – Because my mother entered the room, I had to quickly turn off the computer and go to bed.

Translation method: tracing

9) 금사빠 - formed by adding the first syllables of the words 금방, 사랑에 and 빠지다. Denotes a person who quickly falls in love [14].

넌금사빠네요. - You seem to be one of those who fall in love quickly.

Translation method: descriptive.

10) 알파걸 - formed using the first letter of the Greek alphabet alpha (Greek α) and from the English word girl (girl) [15]. It translates as "leader girl", a successful lady, the first in everything.

Describing powerful girls in leadership positions in society and in the workplace.

현재 사회에 알파걸이 많아졌어요. - In modern society, there are much more female leaders.

Translation method: tracing

CONCLUSION

The semantic analysis of the phrases selected in the course of the study made it possible to divide them according to the degree of fusion of the components into syntactically free and syntactically non-free (phraseological).

The next direction of our research was to identify ways of translating English phrases into English. The analysis showed that 40% of the sample are translated into English using tracing, 40% - descriptive translation, 10% - transcription / transliteration, 10% - selection of equivalent.

Thus, the study revealed that:

1) Nominal Korean neologisms-phrases of the 21st century are free phrases and phraseological units;

2) these phrases are translated into English using tracing, descriptive translation, transcription/transliteration, lexico-semantic transformation.

The obtained results of the study can be used in the further study of neologisms, phrases in newspaper and journalistic texts and social networks. The practical material is structured in a Korean-English dictionary of neologisms (see Appendix).

APPENDIX

Lexical item in Korean	Translation into English	Interpretation
비번	password	An abbreviation for the Korean words 비밀 meaning secret and 번호 meaning number.
버카	Bus card	버스 "bus" and 카드 card", i.e. card for paying for bus fares.
있어빌리티	ability	(a combination of Korean "isso" (there is, there is) and ability (skill, opportunity)). A term that refers to the use of social networks. A certain trend of behavior, which includes ostentatious "glamor", wealth, wealth and beauty of life. "Pretend you have something, even if it's just for show."
앱등이	Fan of Apple products	Due to the widespread use of Apple products, fans of these products are called product fans, or 앱등이.
셀카를 찍다	take a selfie.	It came from the English "selfie", that is, to take pictures of oneself.
핑프 is short for 핑거 프린세스	Finger princess	Derived from an English expression, widely used in the domestic sphere, when describing a person's character
낄낄빠빠	is an abbreviation for the full phrase "낄 때 끼고 빠질 때 빠져". Join when you need to, pass by when you need to	know the right time for your actions
엄크	initial syllables 엄 from the word 엄마 (mother) and 크 from the word "Critical".	the moment in a computer game when the hero dies due to the mother suddenly entering the room.
금사빠	formed by adding the first syllables of the words 금방 (right now), 사랑에 (in love) and 빠지다 (fall)	Denotes a person who quickly falls in love
알파걸	formed using the first letter of the Greek alphabet alpha (Greek α) and from the English word girl (girl). It translates as "leader girl", a successful lady, the first in everything.	Describing powerful girls in leadership positions in society and in the workplace.

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